

ARS3D - How to create a Feature?

Working Paper

Identifier:	DOI 10.17605/OSF.IO/5JHA8
Replaces:	n.a.
Date Issued:	2020/06/25
Date Modified:	2021/11/01
Title:	ARS3D Working document
Subject	ARS, Semantik, Feature
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Format:	application/vnd.google-apps.document application/vnd.google-apps.kix
Language:	en-EN
Relation:	https://www.dfg.de/foerderung/programme/nfdi/ https://www.nfdi4objects.net/ [weitere, verwandte Dokumente, auf die ggf. verwiesen wird]
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About this document

This document describes how to create features, observations, feature groups and interpretations as a part of the BMBF promoted ARS3D project.

The last chapter also describes the ARS3D-Search routine:

<https://ars3d.rgzm.de/objectSearch.htm>

General informations

1. Different types of fields and how to use their functions

Every *free-text* field gets filled manually. Every *dropdown* field gives the possibility to choose the used information. Every statement has a *dropdown* function too, to choose the matching source out of the different authors. If a new field is needed, then use the function “**new ...**”. Before doing this, it must be ensured that this one doesn’t exist already. Every created field only can be deleted from the creator of the programm! Avoid duplications!

Object information:

<i>Object label</i>	Free-text (text editable)
<i>Inventory number</i>	Free-text (text editable)
<i>Type</i>	Dropdown (choose object type)
<i>Shape</i>	Dropdown (+ new shape individual)
<i>Material</i>	Dropdown (+ new material individual)
<i>Condition type</i>	Dropdown (+ new condition type individual)
<i>Manufacturing type</i>	Dropdown (+ new manufacturing type individual)
<i>Findspot</i>	Dropdown (+ new findspot individual)
<i>Residence</i>	Dropdown (+ new residence individual)
<i>Period</i>	Dropdown (+ new period individual)
<i>Groups</i>	Dropdown (+ new object group)
<i>Statement</i>	Add statement of the object Dropdown > select author and statement (+ new statement individual)

Every given information can be edited by changing and saving the selection. Only statements must be deleted completely to select a new one.

Feature:

<i>Feature label</i>	Free-text (text editable)
<i>Feature type</i>	Dropdown (selection editable)
<i>Manufacturing type</i>	Dropdown (+ new manufacturing feature type)
<i>Observation</i>	> <i>ref. Observations</i>

Every feature can be deleted. But every observation or statement inside this feature will be deleted too, so you need to start a completely new feature!

Abraham

label+type manufacturing observation relations geometry process delete feature

>Applique (positive)< applied decorated related to 0 feature(s) and described with 6 observations(s)

Abraham > bearded, holding, holding object, holding sword, looking to the left, standing

Statement > Armstrong 8.207

Statement > Löwenstein männl. Gewandfigur II b

man > bearded, holding, holding object, holding sword, looking to the left, standing

short belted tunic

tunic

Isaac

label+type manufacturing observation relations geometry process delete feature

>Applique (positive)< applied decorated related to 0 feature(s) and described with 6 observations(s)

Statement > Armstrong 8.208

Isaac > beardless, carrying, carrying bag, looking to the right, standing

Statement > Löwenstein männl. Gewandfigur II a

man > beardless, carrying, carrying bag, looking to the right, standing

short belted tunic

tunic

+ new Feature Group

<i>Label</i>	Free-text (text editable)
<i>Group statement</i>	Add statement of the group Dropdown > select author and statement (+ new statement individual)
<i>Feature relations</i>	Dropdown (selection editable)
<i>Group relations</i>	Dropdown (selection editable)

Every group can be deleted. But every feature or statement connected in this group will be deleted too, so you need to start a completely new group!

Abraham and Isaac

label statements feature relations group relations delete group

contains 2 feature(s) and 0 group relation(s) and 0 statement(s)

Feature > Abraham

Feature > Isaac

+ add Observation

<i>Label</i>	Free-text (text editable) = <i>observation item / statement</i>
<i>Observation Item class</i>	Dropdown (choose item class)
<i>Observation Item</i>	Dropdown (+ new item individual)
<i>Activity/Condition</i>	Dropdown (+ new activity / new condition)
<i>Observation statement</i>	Add statement of the feature (= feature statement) Dropdown > select author and statement (+ new statement individual)

Every created observation is made and can't be edited, only deleted as once. Then you need to create a new observation. Always be ensured that the description of observations describing the same thing will be coincident! (> Abraham / man).

+ new Interpretation

<i>Label</i>	Free-text (text editable)
<i>Interpretation arguments</i>	+ add argument > select observation (Dropdown) > select statement > select author and statement (+ new statement individual)

Main = all observations

Supportive = all statements

Every interpretation can be deleted as once, but every argument within will be deleted too. On the other hand, if needed, each argument can also be deleted separately.

2. Creating a new field - How to do with some examples

> Meta-Index ID is always 0!

- + **new shape individual (> object information)**

shape	bowl / dish / mould / ...
meta-index	0

- + **new material individual (> object information)**

material	clay / plaster / ...
meta-index	0

- + **new condition type individual (> object information)**

condition type	complete / fragmented / ...
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- + **new manufacturing type individual (> object information)**

manufacturing type	potter wheel / mould made / ...
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- + **new findspot individual (> object information)**

findspot	unknown / ...
meta-index	0

- + **new residence individual (> object information)**

residence	Römisch-Germanisches-Zentralmuseum
meta-index	0

- + **new period individual (> object information)**

period	Late Antiquity / ...
meta-index	0
date	4.-5. century AD / 430 - 500 AD / ...

- + **new object group (> object information)**

group	dish with martyr (> O.41454a / O.41454b) / ...
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- + **new Manufacturing Feature Type (> feature information)**

label	Applied decorated / stamped decorated / ...
meta-index	0

- + **new item individual (> observation information)**

label	man / flute / Bacchus / bow / ...
meta-index	0

> *Only the item individuals can be created new, the item classes are fixed*

- + **new activity (> observation information)**

E7	holding / running / sitting / ...
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- + **new condition (> object information)**

E3	naked / winged / chained / ...
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- + **new statement individual**

classification number	Armstrong 8.36 / Löwenstein Hercules II / ...
comment	p. 173-174 / S. 458 / ...

> *The statement can be created inside different applications, always the same way*
> *The object statements and feature statements are listed separately!*

How to create a feature?

Basic	Normal polygon-line
Crack	Marks cracks on the object
Edge	Marks edges at the object
Overlap	Marks the overlap of two features
Kink	Marks structural changes at the surface
Supplement	Marks supplements and repaired areas
Surface Damage	Marks damages at the surface

3. Right setting of polygons (O.39770 / O.42129):

The minimum distance between two polygon-points always has to be 2-3mm or more. Don't fall below! It's allowed that the polygon-line of a feature crosses another one, as long as the line doesn't touch any other applique in the near environment (O.39770).

If structural changes and damages at the surface don't affect the applique, then it's necessary NOT to include these areas in the feature. Therefore the minimum distance can be fallen below 2-3mm, but don't touch the applique itself (O.42129).

The yellow line crosses the red one.

The blue line along the structural change.

4. Simplified setting of polygons (O.39713):

As long as the minimum distance to the applique is ensured, the polygon-lines can skip smaller indentations and gaps (yellow line).

5. feature label

Naming the main character, object or motif seen in this *feature*. Mythological or religious Characters who can be recognized, will be named! Proper names are written with a first capital letter (> Bacchus). If something isn't recognizable, then write "unknown" (ref. - p.)

6. feature types

Select the type, which describes the kind of motif. If it's incomplete, then use part:

When the motif is separately manufactured (mould made) and is applied on an object or it's a positive mould made relief decoration, then select 1. or 2.

If the motif is either stamped/pushed in the wet clay or a negative mould made relief decoration, then select 3. or 4.

Complete casts of an object, including the decoration (lamp or plate) or casts of single motifs (applique positiv) are described with 5. or 6.

Every object, or rather motif, which is made to produce a positive or negative of itself (symbols or decoration) is described with 7. or 8.

- 1 . Applique (positive)
- 3 . Applique (negative)
- 5 . Mould
- 7 . Stamp

- 2 . Applique (positive) Part
- 4 . Applique (negative) Part
- 6 . Mould (Part)
- 8 . Stamp (Part)

7. manufacturing type

Select the way the motif is manufactured, based on the kind given from the *feature type*:

If the motif is an *applique positive* and obvious separately manufactured, then select 1.

If the motif is an inscription or decoration made by hand (*applique negative*), then select 2.

If the motif is not separately manufactured, but it's part of the object itself (*applique positive or negative*), then select 3. If the motif is stamped into the object, then select 4. The last one often refers to *applique negatives*, rarely the stamps create an *applique positive*.

- 1. Applied decorated (> applique positive)
- 2. Incised decorated (> applique negative)
- 3. Mould made relief decorated (> applique positive or negative)
- 4. Stamped decorated (> applique negative; rarely applique positive)

The manufacturing type only refers to the ARS ware. Objects like stamps or moulds don't get an assignment to the manufacturing type!

8. Numbering the feature labels (O.39846)

If several *features* show the same object, then number the *feature labels*. View from \triangle !
Select the numbers clockwise, starting from the left side of top (reading direction).

9. Numbering the mould labels (O.41426)

Mould-plates often carry several moulds showing all the same motif. The moulds are usually arranged linearly. Number the *mould labels* in reading direction, line for line. View from \triangle !

10. Numbering of single objects or ornaments (O.40838)

If several small objects or ornaments are distributed between the main motifs, then number them like feature labels too, clockwise, starting from the left side of top (reading direction) > “blossom 1”, “blossom 2”. Objects or ornaments placed very close together will be captured as a group > “blossom 1 (group 1)”, “blossom 2 (group 1)”. Inside these small groups the numbering is clockwise too.

Achilles cycle (O.40838)

11. Special cases

a. O.40743

The dots were manufactured while pushing them from the reverse, noticeable at the front. The dots were captured at the front side as an *applique positive*.

bowl with ornament and dots (O.40743)

b. O.40751 und O.40752

The scratched details on formed shapes (animals or other objects) is captured as one feature (*applique negative*). But for archaeological comparison the objects are unprofitable.

figur ram (O.40751)

figur fish (O.40752)

How to create a *feature group*?

A *feature group* connects several *features* that belong to each other thematically or create specific mythological or religious scenes. Sometimes it's possible that different *feature groups* also can belong to each other. In this case use the *group relation*.

12. *feature group label* (O.41399)

The *feature group label* names the specific mythological or religious scene or the motifs and objects related to each other.

feature relations:

Select the relating features of the feature group.

feature group statement:

If possible, select the *feature group statement*. It's the documentation of this combination of *features* in the literature. If the literature doesn't give this combination, so the *features* only have their own *statements*, then no *feature group statement* will be created!

group relation:

(rarely)

The *group relation* will only be selected, when several closed *feature groups* have a connection to each other. This case is rarely, because of the need of several *features* creating several connected *groups*. The current *group relations* are limited at mythological or religious scenes, often they are lined up in time and create a cyclus (> Achilles cyclus / Hercules cyclus)

How to create the observations?

Every possible given information in this *feature* gets his own *observation*. Even the clothing, equipment, weapons or additional figures. Mythological or religious characters that can be recognized get two *observations*. One naming the character itself (> Bacchus), the other one describes the superior *observation item class* (Human Type > man). In this case, if several *observations* describe the same character, object or motif, the description of activities and conditions has always to be coincident!

13. observation label

The *observation label* depends on the *observation item* you've chosen. The naming of the *observation item* is the *observation label* at the same time.

14. observation item class:

Human type
Mythological or Religious Character
Animal
Clothing
Plant
Ornament
Physical Item
Professional Type
Architectural Element
Furnishing and Equipment
Ancient Weapon
Hybrid
Ceremonial Item
Human Part Type
Musical Instrument
Statement (*ref. observation statement*)

observation item (examples):

> man
> Bacchus
> dog
> tunic
> palm
> lozenges
> basket
> captive
> column
> amphora
> club
> satyr
> thyrsos
> hand
> flute
> Armstrong 8.51

15. activity / condition

Describe the activity and the condition of the current observation, as detailed as possible. The description of two or more observations, referring to the same object or character, has always to be coincident!

Examples of description

Indications of directions follow the point of view from the motif or character!

O.41399

bowl with Paris (clothing > tunic)!

Paris			
✍ manufacturing	✍ observation	✍ relations	✍ geometry process
»Applique (positive)« related to 0 feature(s) and described with 7 observations(s)			
Statement > Löwenstein Parisurteil			
Paris > beardless, holding, holding object, holding object in right hand, looking to the left, sitting, sitting enthroned			
long-sleeved tunic			
man > beardless, holding, holding object, holding object in right hand, looking to the left, sitting, sitting enthroned			
mantle			
phrygian cap			
tunic			

Paris > **tunic + long-sleeved tunic**, mantle, phrygian cap

It's necessary to ensure that every *observation* describing any type of a tunic, gets a second *observation* of the superior class too (shown in example)!

O.39713

bowl with Bacchus and dog

Bacchus			
✍ manufacturing	✍ observation	✍ relations	✍ geometry process
»Applique (positive)« applied decorated related to 0 feature(s) and described with 5 observations(s)			
Statement > Armstrong 8.51			
Bacchus > beardless, holding, holding object, holding rod in left hand, holding vessel in right hand, looking to the right, naked, standing			
dog > barking, looking up, sitting			
man > beardless, holding, holding object, holding rod in left hand, holding vessel in right hand, looking to the right, naked, standing			
thyrsos			

- Mythological Character > Bacchus (observation)
- Human Type > man (observation)
- Animal > dog (observation)
- Ceremonial Item > thyrsos (observation)
- Statement > Armstrong 8.51

16. observation statement (feature statement):

The *statements* are taken from the literature. Literature taken so far: **Atlante 1981, Hayes 1972, Armstrong 1993 und Löwenstein 2015**. Every feature gets its own statement (multiple statements from different authors desirable). There are *statements* for single motifs as well as for complete scenes. Naming the *statements* following these examples:

Armstrong: Armstrong 8.51
 Armstrong 1.24
Atlante: Atlante 8
 Atlante E XVI
Löwenstein: Löwenstein Hercules II
 Löwenstein Venus im Tempel
Hayes: Hayes 120 (ARS)
 Hayes 26 (C' Ware)

> For **Hayes 1972** you need to distinguish between different types. The catalogue of stamps for the African Red Slip Ware is marked as (ARS). The catalogue of stamps for the Late Roman C' Ware is marked as (C' Ware). In a few cases the titles of scenes are given.

How to create the interpretation?

The *interpretation* gives the possibility to belay the identification of mythological or religious characters and scenes you made. Arguments affecting the description of the motif consist of the *observations* you made. Arguments affecting the source out of the literature consist of the *statements* you created.

17. interpretation label

The interpretation label names the character or the scene you've identified.

If possible create two or more interpretations to belay the character and the scene in which he is involved.

18. interpretation arguments

Select every argument documenting the interpretation, including the descriptive *observation items* of the motif as well as his *observation statement* (in an ideal case name both).

Every observation is considered as a **main-argument**, while every statement is **supportive**.

O.39780

bowl with Hercules and the apples of the Hesperides

Hercules	Hercules and the apples of the Hesperides
arguments	
Supportive Argument > Löwenstein Hercules I (Statement)	Supportive Argument > Löwenstein Hercules I (Statement)
Main Argument > bow (Observation)	Supportive Argument > Löwenstein Baum mit Ladon (Statement)
Main Argument > quiver (Observation)	Main Argument > snake (Observation)
Main Argument > club (Observation)	Main Argument > man (Observation)
Main Argument > man (Observation)	Main Argument > tree (Observation)

ARS3D Search

<https://ars3d.rgzm.de/objectSearch.htm>

The ARS3D Search can be used for a targeted search for specific objects.

INPUT

TOTAL: Number of objects found, according to the query.

SORT ATTRIBUTE: The sort attribute of the objects can be selected by label (alphabetical) or inventory number (numerical).

RESULT STYLE ATTRIBUTE: The result style attribute can be chosen between boxes and a list. The boxes also show small preview pictures of the objects.

ACTIVE FILTER: The active filter shows the actual selected keywords. By clicking on them, they will be removed from the active filter.

FILTER LABEL & IDENTIFIER: The filter label & identifier field gives the possibility to search specifically for object labels, feature labels (=feature observation item) and inventory numbers. Use the field “*enter search string*” to type in your question.

FILTER KEYWORDS: The filter keywords are subdivided in object information keywords (dark green) and feature information keywords (light green). The number behind shows the quantity of objects related to this keyword. Choose the needed keywords by clicking on them. They will appear below the active filter. Now the output shows all objects related to the selected keywords.

Example:

The screenshot shows the ARS3D Search interface. At the top, there is a green header with the ARS3D Search logo and text. Below the header, the search results are displayed. The first section shows "TOTAL 5 ARS OBJECTS". Underneath, there are two sections for selection: "SORT ATTRIBUTE" with radio buttons for "label" (selected) and "inventory number"; and "RESULT STYLE ATTRIBUTE" with radio buttons for "boxes" (selected) and "list". Below these, the "ACTIVE FILTER" section shows two green boxes: one for "object period" with the text "Late Antiquity >350/355 - 450/475 AD" and another for "feature observation item" with the text "Achilles".

After questioning the keywords “*Late Antiquity>350/355 - 450/475 AD*” (object period) and “*Achilles*” (feature observation item), the program gets 5 results. These objects are limited to the requested period with a depiction of Achilles on it.

OUTPUT

The results are depicted in small boxes or just listed.
A closer look gives more information about the requested objects.

O.40529

rectangular dish with Achilles cycle

Object Data = Object Information

Object Data go to 3D model	
African Red Slip ware	object type
rectangular dish	shape
clay	shape
fragmented	condition type
mould made	manufacturing type
unknown	findspot
Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum	residence
Late Antiquity (350/355 - 450/475 AD)	period
false	group
Hayes: Hayes 56 from Hayes (1972), p.83-91	statement

The button “*go to 3D model*” leads to the ARS3D Database for detecting the object.

Feature = Feature Information

Feature go to 3D model	
man	label
Applique (positive)	feature type
n/a	manufacturing type
2020-06-16T13:14:56.969+02:00	creation date
Achilles: holding object in right hand,holding spear,looking back,naked,running	observation
man: holding object in right hand,holding spear,looking back,naked,running	observation
Armstrong 9.3A-D	statement
Hayes Achilles cycle	statement
Löwenstein Entdeckung Achills auf Skyros	statement

Every single feature created on this object has its own entry.

The button “*go to 3D model*” leads to the ARS3D Database for detecting the object.

Metadata: Including object label and inventory number